

PERCEPTION OF CINEMA AND FILM WATCHING HABITS OF UNDERGRADUATE STUDENTS IN KHYBER PAKHTUNKHWA

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Abstract

This study investigated the Perception of Cinema and Film Watching Habits of Undergraduate Students in Southern Khyber Pakhtunkhwa province. It aimed to determine the perception of cinema, film watching preferences (content wise) and the way they prefer watching movies. Cross-sectional survey method of research was applied to conduct the study and questionnaire was used as a data collection tool. The data was collected from 150 respondents through random sampling technique. The data indicated that 71.3% of the respondents were engaged at times to watch movies from time to time but the study found that cinema was not preferred by majority of the respondents as more than 70% stated they don't prefer watching movies at cinema. As an alternative source to watch movies the majority 55.3% respondents replied that they accessed android phones for the said purpose. The data analysis showed that most of the respondents enjoyed watching films alone and more than 37% respondents liked comedy genre.

Introduction

Cinema lodges a vital place in the context of power relations within a social formation (Bingham, 1999). It is one of most attractive entertainment forum that holds an important role in building and propelling for systematized civilization (Moti, 2004). Cinema or film is an entertainment medium, and simultaneously it's also a source of information, education, propaganda and opinion-forming. Cinema role cannot be overlooked and it serve as one of the most recognized tool of mass media which is most effective because of its peculiar nature of affording both audio and video aspects to the audience thereby making it very appealing to both the eye and the ear (Elsaesser, 2002).

Movies, in other words also known as films, comes under the category of visual communication use both moving pictures and sounds in an attempt to give audience something significant as a story or teaching. That is why it is one of those mediums that are held at an apex among others in the domain of being sources of entertainment, information, and education (Baiju, 2019; Lehman & Luhr, 2018). In his research work (Moti, 2004) mentioned movies as a medium in the context of capable of bringing about social change in society and serve as a platform for information and education. He stated further that films are doing meaningful work by coming up with a combination of facts, selected, from real life experiences mingled with emotions wherein a world, based on logic and psychological facts, is created that give a sense of feeling beautiful to its viewers along with emotionally educating them.

According to SÁGVÁRI (2009), films and cinemas play an important role in modern societies for all generations in general and particularly the younger ones. Whereas Diefendorff and Chandler (2011) stated that movies leaves an impact on personality and affiliated specific behaviors (Ahmad, Shafi & Shah, 2016). (Ganti, 2004) mentioned that the unique characteristics of going to the cinema bears a significant impact on mental health. Due to visual stimulation as films can create, cinema can have effects on mental well-being that is affiliated with emotions. The collective emotions experience through cinema movie watching affords safe environment that can give us of roles and emotions that may not be experienced otherwise.

According to Studlar, G. (1984) Cinema gratify visual pleasure and the explicitly of visualization encompassing aspects of sex, violence and crime has yielded the industry into a capital machine. Erosion of value system and celebrities turning into commodities and hegemonic ideologies gaining more representation as well as portrayal of women as a fragile, submissive and vulnerable traits are also the other aspects of cinema. Keeping in views the aforementioned importance reflected in various literature studies, in his research work (Gazda, 1997) stated that Lollywood film industry was established in Pakistani with scant resources at hand as India used to be a center of the film industry. From the beginning Pakistani film producers and directors have depicted social realities through the use of cinema and considerable number of notable films have been produced, orbiting social, political and

religious issues. Up until the 1980s, on average 80 films were produced each year that was a golden era of Pakistani cinema. Later, the film industry in Pakistan shrank due to numerous factors. Waves of feminism also had an enormous impact on the Pakistani film industry on an international level. The film "Aurat Raaj" shows the hegemonic position and role of women. Because in Pakistan, society is patriarchal was also ensured and the notion gets further strength through the lens of media turning it into acceptability as a conventional ideology, Gazda added.

Buckland (2011) rightly mentioned that all the films, worldwide, produced correspond to ideologies in reality. The Oxford dictionary defines ideology as political, religious, social and economic ideas eschewed by a specific collection of people or communities. Likewise, films are the propellers of promoting, and propagating some ideologies. Any stand against the accepted ideologies, call incitement to debate. The revival of cinema in Pakistan brought about drastic changes in production techniques and storylines. Most of the films dealt with issues pertaining to social problems as in the wake of 9/11 incident terrorism engulfed a major topic for the film industry across the world wherein Muslims gets tagging and portrayed as terrorists.

According to Pakistan statistical yearbook (2019) report there were a total of 95 cinema halls till 2018 and the number decreased to 72 in the year 2019 in the country. The absence of cinema in the area is not enough notations that people do not desire to go to cinema.

In his research work (Athique 2011) stated that the parameters shifted from traditional cinemas into the more modern multiplexes. Cinema crowds were formed in India as against the earlier elite and privileged class occupation of cinema movie watching places and with passage of time more cinemas sprung up with easy accessibility to all kith and kin. However, gender-based segregation followed as a legacy of earlier and pre-existing culture of class-based exclusion. Research entitled "Movie watching preferences and patterns" was conducted to examine the patterns and preferences of Female students viz-a-viz movie watching including to locate genres of movies they watch mostly and determined that movie watching has become integral part of their lives without which they cannot think their lives are completed (Momen, Ali Khuhro & Gul, 2021) stated. Hirschman and Holbrook (1982) share that it is the audience sensations, emotions and other aspects of life experiences that relates to viewers choices and preferences about the movie genres. Need and preference of viewers are the factors that determined choice of movie genre, added Zufryden (1996).

Khan, Adnan, Hussain & Tariq (2015) conducted a study entitled "Decline of cinema in Pakistan" and found that film watching at cinemas are on the decline in the country and viewers opined that due to sub-standard production that decline cinematic viewership. While listing other causes of film declination in Pakistan at cinemas, along with scarcity of professional and good writers, the

research work found that availability of other digital gadgets including android mobile phones are also the causative agents of cinema decline in the country.

The research conducted by the Momen et al., (2021) evaluated movie watching habits and found that over two-fifths of responses falls in the category of watching films with the help of mobile phones, rest follows through laptop use, television and certain other digital equipment's in this regard. In the same research work they also found that majority watches films at home, followed by those who visit to cinemas while a proportion of respondents replied it with hostels wherein they watch movies and at friends home. The research study conducted by the Khan et al., (2015) entitled "Decline of cinema in Pakistan" determined that two fourth of respondents with leading frequency were exposed to Indian films, while very less proportion of respondents watch Pakistani movies. The data also revealed that those watching films solely were the larger wardership, followed by those who prefer watching films with family and the rest with friends and colleagues or co-workers. Similarly those watching films at homes stood in majority while cinema movie watching followed next and rest liked to watch films at hotels etc. Regarding genre of film preference of love story films were in the leading while action movies and comedy films followed suits.

Zoltan and Lakatos (2011) mentioned watching movies are directly related psychological behavior of individuals and added that in case of one might not come across finding legal means of watching movie, he would find way out by resorting to free sources or resort to pirated version of movies for want of satisfying his psychological needs. Given this backdrop, the present research work aimed to explore students perceptions in the Southern Khyber Pakhtunkhwa province about the value of big film screens i.e cinemas. Apart from other parts of the province and the country at large, several districts of Southern Khyber Pakhtunkhwa province including Kohat, Bannu, Tank and Dera Ismail Khan also hosted cinemas. This current study focusses on that whether watching cinema is still a trend and movie watchers still consider it as an important place to visit. The basic theme of the study was to examine and know the perception of the undergraduate students about the cinema and to determine their film viewing habits.

The researchers could not come across any such study that may dwell on the context of examining perception regarding cinema and film watching habits in this part of the region. The study endeavored to profile habits and perceptions about watching movies through cinema, how and what type of content they access for watching films/movies and other mediums of watching films and certain other choices of the respondents were investigated in the study. There are a few researches, conducted on cinema and its various aspects in Pakistan. It will be valuable addition from southern part of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan. Pakistan has a huge chunk of conservatives and religious society. There are less than 100 cinemas across the country. In this scenario, examining the perception of cinema film

watching habits and preferences will help future researchers to predict the future of cinema and film viewing habits in such like regions. It will benefit the researchers who want to conduct cinema or film impact researches in the region. This is the first cinema and film related profile research in this region.

Methodology

The current research study has been conducted under the umbrella of 'Uses and Gratification Theory', by Elihu Katz, Michael Gurevitch and Jay Blumber in 1974s that provides bases on media consumption. Cross-sectional study was conducted, through a questionnaire formed according to the objective and research questions of the study. It contained comprising closed-ended, and multiple-choice questions. The questionnaire was distributed to 150 undergraduate students in Southern Khyber Pakhtunkhwa regions of district Kohat, Karak, Bannu and Lakki Marwat. Data was collected from respondents through random sampling survey technique.

Ever been to Cinema

Category	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	32	21.3%
No	118	78.7%
Total	150	100

The table data determined that 21.3% of the respondent's visited cinema while 78.7% of the respondents were not exposed to cinema going either. It was determined that very less ratio of students had been to cinema for watching any movie.

City you visited cinema

Category	Frequency	Percentage
Peshawar	21	14%
Islamabad	14	9.3%
Lahore	11	7.3%
Southern Khyber Pakhtunkhwa	104	69.3%
Total	150	100

The data reflects that there were 14% respondents who went to cinema at Peshawar, 9.3% of the respondents at Islamabad, 7.3% at Lahore, and 69.3% mentioned Southern Khyber Pakhtunkhwa including Kohat, Bannu and D.I. Khan regions.

Likeness to watch movies in cinema

Category	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	44	29.3%
No	106	70.7%
Total	150	100

The data revealed that 29.3% of the respondents liked to watch movies in cinema whereas majority of 70.7% of the respondents do not like to watch movies in cinema.

Watching movies/films

Category	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	107	71.3%
No	43	28.7%
Total	150	100

The data indicated that 71.3% of the respondents were engaged in watching movies while the 28.7% of the respondents replied in 'No'.

Alternate sources you use for watching films?

Category	Frequency	Percentage
TV	22	14.7%
Android Phones	83	55.3%
Laptops	26	17.3%
Any other	19	12.7%
Total	150	100

The data revealed that 14.7% of the respondents used TV to watch films, 55.3% respondent's accessed android phones, 17.3% respondents marked laptops, and 12.7% answered any other. Among various sources, majority of the respondents accessed the films through their android phones following the laptops with second majority.

Movie watching habits

Category	Frequency	Percentage
Alone	85	56.7%
Friends	38	25.3%
Strangers	4	2.7%
Any other	23	15.3%
Total	150	100

The table shows that 56.7% of the respondents watching film alone, 25.3% respondents replied with friends, 2.7% mentioned strangers and 15.3% of the respondents answered any other.

Movie preferences

Category	Frequency	Percentage
Action/thriller	36	24%
Comedy/Funny	58	38.7%
Drama/romantic	32	21.3%

Any other	24	16%
Total	150	100

Data shows that 24% of the respondents watched Action/thriller movies, 38.7% of the respondents marked Comedy/Funny, 21.3% responded to Drama/romantic and 16% watched any other genre of movies.

Impact on real life actions

Category	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	135	90
No	15	10
Total	150	100

According to the table, among total, 90 % of the respondents thought that movies has impact on real life actions whereas 10% marked No, as they thought that movies has no impact on real life actions.

Best medium for watching films

Category	Frequency	Percentage
Cinema	24	16%
Other Gadgets (TV, mobiles, laptops etc.)	126	84%
Total	150	100

The table data revealed that 16% of the respondent's marked cinema as the best medium for watching films and 84% responded to other gadgets (TV, mobiles, laptops, etc.). Hence it proves that TV, mobile and laptops etc. are preferred as best medium among majority of the respondents. The majority respondents mentioned that gadgets like TV, Mobile phones, laptops are modern equipment and they prefer to access those for watching films. These sources are easily accessible and also personal, where one can view movie of his/her choice.

Conclusion

The survey data of the research study fetch us to the conclusion that very less ratio of students have visited cinema either in this part of the region in the province of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. The study told us that socializing on the eve of watching films was not a prefer mode by respondents but to watch movie alone was their preference. Concerning to the genre of films, most of the students said that they liked comedy movies, while second highest number of respondents liked action movies as a trend here in this part of the region among the population concerned.

Yet another trend that the study found was most of the students were engaged in watching movies through modern digital accessories. Concerning to the film watching, majority were found using android phone, seconded by laptops, and several responded to TV while few mentioned Tablets and

desktop computers. The latest digital equipment's were preferred as it is easily accessible and can watch films of own choice.

Movie watching trend at cinemas exists to a lesser degree in this part of the region and the study found that films impact one's real-life actions as majority of the respondents replied that movies affect their real-life actions. The study reflects dwindling prospects and even declining trends to socialize by resorting to cinemas for movie watching. As the study mostly dwelt on trends, habits and perceptions of movie watching mainly focusing on locating movie watching trends at cinemas, it can prove as a harbinger for further research work in to locate the actual cause and effects of dwindling trends of movie watching in cinemas as against the importance of watching movie at cinema reflected in literature review of the current study.

References

- Abend, Gabriel. (26June 2008) "The Meaning of Theory." *Sociological Theory*: 173- 199.
- Ahmad M U., & Hussain, S. (2012). New Media trends among ODL students in Pakistan and their impacts on learning.
- Ahmad, S., Shafi, B., & Shah, M. (2016). Viewing patterns of movies and the adoption of deviant behavior among young students. *Pakistan Journal of Criminology*, 8(1), 17-27.
- Ali, A. (2012). The Portrayal of Women in Pakistan feature Films Urdu and Punjabi (1988-1999) A Critical Evaluation. An unpublished Ph.D. thesis, Department of Media Studies, The Islamia University of Bahawalpur, Pakistan.
- Aqsa. I. S (2015). A Feminist Representation in Pakistani Cinema: A Case Study of "Bol" The Movie. *New Media and Mass Communication*, 2224-3275 (Online).
- Bachaana (2016). A film directed by Nasir Khan and Rizwan Saeed, Big Film Entertainment,
- Baiju, G. (2019). A comparative study on the impact of new media in the movie viewing habits of youth and middle age. *Indian Journal of Research*, 7.
- Bashir Memon, Rashid Ali Khuhro, Saman Gul (2021) Movie Watching Preferences and Patterns: A Survey of the Female Students University of Sindh, Jamshoro, *Journal of media and communication studies Pakistan* Volume 1, Issue 2. July 2021
- Bearden, W. O., & Etzel, M. J. (1982). Reference group influence on product and brand purchase decisions. *Journal of consumer research*, 9(2), 183-194.
- Bingham, D. (1999). I do want to live: Female voices, male discourse, and Hollywood Biopics. *Cinema Journal*, 3(38), 3-26. Books.
- Blumler, J. G., Katz, E. (1974). *Uses of Mass Communications: Current Perspectives on Gratifications Research*, Sage, Beverly Hills, CA.

- Chen, Y., Gao, Q., & Rau, P.-L. P. (2017). Watching a movie alone yet together: Understanding reasons for watching Danmaku videos. *International Journal of Human-Computer Interaction*, 33(9), 731-743.
- Cross-Sectional Study | Definition, Uses & Examples Published on May 8, 2020 by Lauren Thomas. Revised on July 21, 2022.
- Deák, D.(2008). A világhalo Lumiere-jei. Retrieved from http://filmvilag.hu/xista_frame.php?cikk_id=9215
- Diefendorff, J. M., & Chandler, M. M. (2011). Motivating employees. In S. Zedeck (Ed.), *Maintaining, expanding, and contracting the organization* (Vol. 3, pp. 2300). New York: American Psychological Association.
- Elsaesser T. and Buckland W. (2002). *Studying Contemporary, American Films, A guide to movie analysis*, New York: Oxford University press.
- Fischhoff, S., Antonio, J., & Lewis, D. (1998). Favorite films and film genres as a function of race, age, and gender. *Journal of Media Psychology*, 3(1), 1-9.
- Fuller, Kathryn H. 1996. *At the Picture Show; Small-Town Audiences and the Creation of Movie Fan Culture*. By the Smithsonian Institute
- Ganti, T. (2004). *Bollywood: Guidebook to popular Hindi Cinema*. London, New York: Routledge.
- Gantz, W., & Wenner, L. A. (1991). Men, women, and sports: Audience experiences and effects. *Journal of Broadcasting & Electronic Media*, 35(2), 233-243.
- Gazdar, Mushtaq (1997) *Pakistan Cinema (1947- Karachi* , Oxford University Press.
- Harvey, L., 2012-22, *Social Research Glossary*, Quality Research International, <http://www.qualityresearchinternational.com/socialresearch/>
- Hirschman, E. C., & Holbrook, M. B. (1982). Hedonic consumption: Emerging concepts, methods and propositions. *Journal of Marketing*, 46(3), 92-101.
- Hofmeister-Toth, A., & Torocsik, M. (1996). *Fogyasztói magatartás: Nemzeti Tankönyvkiadó*.
- Horvath, A, Gyenge, B., & Racz, G. (2015). Movie viewing habits of university students. 3(1), 1-131. doi:10.17626/dBEM.ICoM.P00.2015.p099.
- Horvath, A., & Gyenge, B. (2017). Movie consumption among Hungarian university students. *Annals of Marketing Management & Economics*, 3(1), 1-131.
- Horvath, A., Gyenge, B., & Racz, G. (2017). Entertainment of young generation: movie viewing habits. In *Management, organizations and society*. Budapest: Agro inform.

- James, M. L., & Wotring, C. E. (1995). An Exploratory Study of the Perceived Benefits of Electronic Bulletin Board Use and Their Impact on Other Communication Activities. *Journal of Broadcasting & Electronic Media*, 39, 30-50.
- Kallet, Richard H. (October 2004) "How to Write the Methods Section of a Research Paper." *Respiratory Care* 49: 1229-1232.
- Kaplan, S. J. (1978). The Impact of Cable Television Services on the Use of Competing Media. *Journal of Broadcasting*, 22, 155-165.
- Khan, Ali & Ahmad, A. N. (2016). *Cinema and society: Film and social change in Pakistan*. Oxford University Press.
- Khan, D. W., Adnan, M., Hussain, S., & Tariq M. (2015). Decline of Film Industry in Pakistan, Causes and future Prospects. *International Journal of Information technology & engineering*
- Klarer, Mario. 1999. *An Introduction to Literary Studies*. London: Routledge.
- Lehman, P., & Luhr, W. (2018). *Thinking about movies: Watching, questioning, enjoying* (Fourth Edition ed.). New Jersey WILEY Blackwell.
- Maxfield, S. M. (2003). *Media at the movies: Analyzing the movie-viewing audience*. (Master), University of Florida, Florida.
- Momen, B., Ali Khuhro, R., & Gul, S. (2021). Movie Watching Preferences and Patterns. A survey of female Students in University of Sindh Jomshoro, Pakistan. *MCS, Journal of Media and Communication Studies*, Vol 1(2 July 2021).
- Moti, G. (2004). *Indian Popular Cinema: A narrative of cultural change*. USA: Trentham
- Parveen, D. U., Tariq, T., & Siddiqui, M. T. (2015). Pakistani Cinema: Seventy years of Rise and Fall. *Journal of Mass Communication*, Vol 12(May 2015).
- Robinson, J. P., Kestnbaym, M., Neustadtl, A., & Alvarez, A. (2000). Mass Media Use and Social Life among Internet Users. *Social Science Computer Review*, 18, 490-501.
- Sage Qualitative Research methods. <https://methods.sagepub.com/reference/sage-encyc-qualitative-research-methods>
- Sagvari, B. (2009). Fanta TrendRiport VI: Muzsak vonzasaban” Kultura–a mediafogyasztasi szokasoka fiatalok koreben. Retrieved from <https://www.scribd.com/doc/38774721/fantatrendriport6-091026062651phpapp02>
- Severny, Andrei (September 5, 2013). "The Movie Theater of the Future Will Be In Your Mind". Tribeca. Archived from the original on September 7, 2013. Retrieved September 5, 2013.
- Studlar, G. (1984). Masochism and the Perverse Pleasures of the Cinema. *Quarterly Review of Film & Video*, 9(4), 267-282.
- Thomas, L, (2022). Cross sectional study | Definition, uses and examples. Scribber (2022)

- Welman, C., Kruger, F., & Mitchell, B. (2005). *Research methodology*. Cape Town: Oxford University Press.
- Wimmer, D. R. & Dominick, R. J. (1994). *Mass Media Research; An Introduction* (4th Ed). Belmont, CA: Wadsworth.
- Wiseman, J. P., & Aron, M. S. (1970). *Field projects for sociology students*. New York: HarperCollins Publishers.
- Wiseman, J. P., & Aron, M. S. (1970). *Field projects for sociology students*. New York: HarperCollins Publishers.
- Zoltan, B., & Lakatos, B. (2011). A filmek online feketepiacá és a moziforgalmazás. *Szociológiai Szemle*, 21(2), 111-140.
- Zufryden, F. S. (1996). Linking advertising to box office performance of new film releases. A marketing planning model. *Journal of Advertising Research*, 36(4), 2942.